

Endorsements

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Individual Endorsements

First Name	Last Name	Affiliated Organization	Post date
Iris	Alfredsson	Swedish National Data Service	Jun 20, 2019
Jeremy	Chaz rosette	Mokedmexia	Sep 30, 2018
Ben	Newman Wright	UK Data Archive	Nov 13, 2015
Hilde	Orten	Norwegian Social Science Data Services (NSD)	Sep 22, 2015
Louise	Corti	UK Data Service	Sep 21, 2015
Steven	McEachern	Director, Australian Data Archive	Jul 27, 2015
Gina	Cheung	UM SRC-SRO	Jan 19, 2015
Brigitte	Hausstein	GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences / da ra	Dec 17, 2014
Wolfgang	Zenk-Möltgen	GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences	Dec 12, 2014
S	Brown	Royal Statistical Society	Dec 4, 2014
Robert	Pratt	Ipsos MORI	Nov 25, 2014

First Name	Last Name	Affiliated Organization	Post date
Eric	Balster	CentERdata	Nov 19, 2014
Mel	Bartley	ESRC International Centre for Life Course Studies, UCL	Nov 19, 2014
Tito	Castillo	Xperimint Ltd	Nov 19, 2014
Noriko	Cable	University College London	Nov 19, 2014
Barry	Radler	University of Wisconsin-Madison	Nov 19, 2014
Dan	Smith	Colectica	Nov 19, 2014
Marion	Wittenberg	Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)	Nov 18, 2014
Tom W.	Snith	NORC at the University of Chicago	Nov 18, 2014
John F	Hall	(None) Retired academic survey researcher http://surveyresearch.weebly.com/	Nov 17, 2014
Jon	Stiles	UC DATA, UC Berkeley	Nov 17, 2014

Organization Endorsements

Organization Name	Organization Logo Image	Post date
UK Data Service		Nov 21, 2015

Organization Name	Organization Logo Image	Post date
Uk Data Archive		Nov 21, 2015
Australian Data Archive		Jul 27, 2015
Metis Ricerche srl		May 19, 2015
Survey Research Operations, Survey Research Center, Institute for Social Research		Feb 12, 2015
University of Wisconsin Research Data Services		Jan 20, 2015
UW-Madison Research Data Services		Jan 2, 2015
da ra - Registration Agency for social and economic data		Dec 17, 2014
GESIS - Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences		Dec 12, 2014
NatCen Social Research		Dec 4, 2014
Ipsos MORI		Nov 25, 2014
Colectica - DDI Survey Design Software		Nov 19, 2014
CentERdata		Nov 19, 2014
Xperimint Ltd.		Nov 18, 2014

Organization Name	Organization Logo Image	Post date
UK Data Service		Nov 10, 2014
Gauthier		Nov 7, 2014
CLOSER (Cohort & Longitudinal Studies Enhancement Resources)		Nov 6, 2014
Centre for Longitudinal Studies, Institute of Education		Nov 6, 2014
Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR)		Nov 4, 2014

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